

The Effects of Transformational Leadership, Adversity Quotient, and Competency on Polri Educators' Performances

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to comprehensively analyse the effects of transformational leadership, adversity quotient and competency on Polri educators' performance. The method used in this study was quantitative approach, survey method and path analysis technique. The dependent variable (endogenous) was Polri Educators' Performances (Y); independent variables (exogenous) were Transformational Leadership (X₁), Adversity Quotient (X₂), and Competency (X₃). The sampling used was simple random sampling. The population in this study was 1,279 educational personnel in the Lemdiklat Polri with total sample of 305 educators. Based on statistical analysis using path analysis, there were direct and indirect effects of exogenous variables (Transformational Leadership, Adversity Quotient, and Competency) on endogenous variable (Polri Educators' Performance). This study suggested that transformational leadership, adversity quotient and competency can increase the performances of police educators.

Keywords: *Transformational Leadership, Adversity Quotient, Competency, Polri Educators' Performances.*

INTRODUCTION

Polri (the National Police), as a civilian institution, is faced with varied tasks as consequences of strategic environment development that occurs at the national, regional and global scope. The development of technology, in addition to having positive impact on the sustainability of national development and improving people's welfare, it can also cause negative excesses in the form of various disturbances in security and public order.

Aware of those matters, the National Police Education and Training Institute forms an educational unit which plays very important role in the implementation of education in the environment. The educational process at the National Police Education and Training Institute certainly requires various supports, one of which is the presence of professional and competent educators. With the existence of professional and competent educational staffs, they will be able to help the students in facing the current challenges in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 towards the 5.0 era.

Improving the performances of educators through human resources (HR) is inseparable from competency, transformational leadership and adversity quotient (Kallapadee, Tesaputa, & Somprach, 2017). Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by a person in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him (Colquitt, Lepine, & Wesson, 2014). Educators' performance in an educational institution is an interesting factor to study for three reasons. They are: first, educators determine the success of teaching and learning process. Without qualified educators, it is impossible for teaching and learning process to produce quality students. Second, educators do not only play a role in transferring knowledge to students but also as role models for attitudes, speech and behaviour. Third, the quality of educators' performance is not permanent but it can be improved in accordance with their own or institutional expectations. Furthermore, any improvement in educational quality which is directed at qualitative changes must place educators at the central point because their role is very strategic and has great responsibility to actualize the goals of national education. Educators' performance can also be seen from the participation of existing human resources by carrying out tasks with a sense of responsibility and discipline. Performance is influenced by internal and external factors. Internal factors include: motivation, job satisfaction, and ability, level of stress, skills, and organizational commitment (Lussier, 2012). Meanwhile, the external factors are organizational culture, work culture, supervision, and transformational leadership.

METHOD

This study was carried out in educational units under the auspices of the National Police Education and Training Center. These educational units are *Lemdiklat, Sespim, STIK, Akpol, Setukpa, Diklat Reserse, Pusdik Lantas, Pusdik Sabhara, Pusdik Brimob, Pusdik Intel, Pusdik Min, Pusdik Binmas, Pusdik, Sebasia, Pusdik Polair, and Sepolwan* with population of 1,279 people. The sample taken was 305 people. This study used quantitative approach, survey method and path analysis

technique. Variables in path analysis consist of exogenous and endogenous variables. The framework of this study is as follows:

Figure 1. Path Analysis Constelation

Description:

- X₁ = Transformasional Leadership
- X₂ = Adversity Quetient
- X₃ = Competency
- Y = Educators' Performances

RESEARCH RESULT

The effect of X₁ (Transformasional Leadership) on Y (Educators' Performances)

The information about transformational leadership on the educators' performances which was given to 305 respondents was obtained from the results of the frequency distribution of data for the interval class group. The transformational leadership values were as follows: the highest was 185; the lowest was 69; average (\bar{X}) was 165.95; standard deviation (s) = 18.582; mode (Mo) = 181; and median (Me) = 173.00.

Simple linear regression analysis with research data pairs between transformational leadership variable (X₁) and educators' performances (Y) produced regression coefficient of 0.346 and constant of 74.626. Thus, the form of the effect of transformational leadership (X₁) on educators' performances (Y) has the following regression equation: $\hat{Y} = 74.626 + 0.346 X_1$.

Next, the significance test and linearity of regression model of transformational leadership on educators' performances were carried out. The test results concluded that the shape of the effect of transformational leadership (X₁) on educators' performances (Y) was linear and significant.

The calculation result of the correlation coefficient between transformational leadership (X₁) and educators' performances (Y) was the simple correlation coefficient of $r_{X_1Y} = 0.332$.

So, it can be concluded that the correlation coefficient $r_{X_1Y} = 0.332$ was significant, meaning that there was positive effect of transformational leadership on educators' performances, with determination coefficient of $r^2_{X_1Y} = 0.344$. This meant that 34.4% of the variation in educators' performances (Y) was influenced by transformational leadership (X₁).

The effect of X₂ (Adversity Quotient) on Y (Educators' Performances)

The information about adversity quotient on the educators' performances which was given to 305 respondents was obtained from the results of the frequency distribution of data for the interval class group. The adversity quotient values were as follows: the highest was 160; the lowest was 54; average (\bar{X}) = 129.06; standard deviation (s) = 20.1; mode (Mo) = 160; and median (Me) = 128.00.

Simple linear regression analysis with research data pairs between adversity quotient variable (X₂) and educators' performances (Y) produced regression coefficient of 0.181 and constant of 108.665. Thus, the form of the effect of adversity quotient (X₂) on educators' performances (Y) has the following regression equation: $\hat{Y} = 108.665 + 0.181 X_2$.

Next, the significance test and linearity of regression model of adversity quotient on educators' performances were carried out. The test results concluded that the shape of the effect of adversity quotient (X₂) on educators' performances (Y) was linear and significant.

The calculation result of the correlation coefficient between adversity quotient (X₂) and educators' performances (Y) was the simple correlation coefficient of $r_{X_2Y} = 0.332$.

So, it can be concluded that the correlation coefficient $r_{x_2y} = 0.332$ was significant, meaning that there was positive effect of adversity quotient on educators' performances, with determination coefficient of $r^2_{x_2y} = 0.110$. This meant that 11.0% of the variation in educators' performances (Y) was influenced by adversity quotient (X_2).

The effect of X_3 (Competency) on Y (Educators' Performances)

The information about competency on the educators' performances which was given to 305 respondents was obtained from the results of the frequency distribution of data for the interval class group. The competency values were as follows: the highest was 190; the lowest was 116; average (\bar{X}) = 180.54; standard deviation (s) = 13.21; mode (Mo) = 190; and median (Me) = 186.00.

Multiple linear regression analysis on research data pairs between competency variable (X_3) and educators' performances (Y) produced regression coefficient of 0.741 and constant of -1.780. Thus, the form of the effect of competency (X_3) on educators' performances (Y) has the following regression equation: $\hat{Y} = -1.780 + 0.741 X_3$.

The calculation result of the correlation coefficient between competency (X_3) and educators' performances (Y) was the simple correlation coefficient of $r_{x_3y} = 0.894$.

So, it can be concluded that the correlation coefficient $r_{x_3y} = 0.894$ was significant, meaning that there was positive effect of competency on educators' performances, with determination coefficient of $r^2_{x_3y} = 0.800$. This meant that 80.0% of the variation in educators' performances (Y) was influenced by competency (X_3).

The effect of X_1 (Transformational Leadership) on X_3 (Competency)

Based on the results of the study, it was obtained that multiple linear regression analysis of the data pairs between the variables X_1 (transformational leadership) and X_3 (competency) was regression coefficient of 0.420 and constant of 110.854. Thus, the form of the effect of transformational leadership (X_1) on competency (X_3) has the following regression equation: $\hat{Y} = 110.8540 + 0.420 X_3$.

The calculation result of the correlation coefficient between transformational leadership (X_1) and competency (X_3) was the simple correlation coefficient of $r_{x_{13}} = 0.591$.

So, it can be concluded that the correlation coefficient $r_{x_{13}} = 0.591$ was significant, meaning that there was positive effect of transformational leadership on competency, with determination coefficient of $r^2_{x_{13}} = 0.349$. This meant that 34.9% of the variation in competency (X_3) was influenced by transformational leadership (X_1).

The effect of X_2 (Adversity Quotient) on X_3 (Competency)

Based on the results of the study, it was obtained that multiple linear regression analysis of the data pairs between the variables X_2 (adversity quotient) and X_3 (competency) was regression coefficient of 0.193 and constant of 155.577. Thus, the form of the effect of adversity quotient (X_2) on competency (X_3) has the following regression equation: $\hat{Y} = 155.577 + 0.193 X_3$.

The calculation result of the correlation coefficient between adversity quotient (X_2) and competency (X_3) was the simple correlation coefficient of $r_{x_{23}} = 0.294$.

So, it can be concluded that the correlation coefficient $r_{x_{23}} = 0.294$ was significant, meaning that there was positive effect of adversity quotient on competency, with determination coefficient of $r^2_{x_{23}} = 0.087$. This meant that 8.7% of the variation in competency (X_3) was influenced by adversity quotient (X_2).

The effect of X_1 (Transformational Leadership) on X_2 (Adversity Quotient)

Multiple linear regression analysis on research data pairs between transformational leadership variable (X_1) and adversity quotient (X_2) produced regression coefficient of 0.322 and constant of 75.671. Thus, the form of the effect of transformational leadership (X_1) on adversity quotient (X_2) has the following regression equation: $\hat{Y} = 75.671 + 0.322 X_2$.

The calculation result of the correlation coefficient between transformational leadership (X_1) and adversity quotient (X_2) was the simple correlation coefficient of $r_{x_{12}} = 0.297$.

So, it can be concluded that the correlation coefficient $r_{x_{12}} = 0.297$ was significant, meaning that there was positive effect of transformational leadership on adversity quotient, with determination coefficient of $r^2_{x_{12}} = 0.088$. This meant that 8.8% of the variation in adversity quotient (X_2) was influenced by transformational leadership (X_1).

In the normality test using the Liliefors test, the criteria were determined through H_0 was acceptable if there was possibility equal or higher value than the critical value at predetermined alpha (α) significance level $\alpha = 0.05$; or if $L_{count} \leq L_{table}$. H_1 is rejected if $L_{count} > L_{table}$.

Table 1. Summary of Normality Test

Variabel	N	L _{count}	L _{table}	Conclusion
X ₁	305	0.089	0.0539	Normal
X ₂	305	0.163	0.0539	Normal
X ₃	305	0.186	0.0539	Normal
Y	305	0.174	0.0539	Normal

From the overall result of normality test from 305 respondents, which includes the Transformational Leadership variable (X₁), the Adversity Quotient variable (X₂), and the Educators' Performances variable (Y), it concluded that every value was $L_{count} < L_{table}$. Thus, it can be concluded that all data from each variable was normally distributed or H₀ is accepted.

GFI is a non-statistical measure that has range value between 0 (*poor fit*) to 1.0 (*perfect fit*). A high value in the index indicates "*better fit*" and a model can be said to be *very good* if the GFI value is higher than or equal to 0.90. The value generated in this study was 0.773 so it does not include to *very good fit*.

Based on the results of data calculation as shown in the table below, the path coefficient value for each path was obtained in Table 2 below:

Table 2. The Significance of the Correlation Coefficient

Path	Correlation Coefficient	t _{count}	t _{table} α = 0,05	Description
ρ _{y1}	0.332	12.618	1.645	Significant
ρ _{y2}	0.332	6.121	1.645	Significant
ρ _{y3}	0.894	34.761	1.645	Significant
ρ ₃₁	0.591	12.750	1.645	Significant
ρ ₃₂	0.294	5.362	1.645	Significant
ρ ₂₁	0.297	5.424	1.645	Significant

RESEARCH DISCUSSION

The Effect of X₁ (Transformational Leadership) on Y (Educators' Performances)

Based on the simple linear regression analysis with pairs of data between transformational leadership variable (X₁) and educators' performances variable (Y) produced regression coefficient of 0.346 and constant of 74.626. Thus, the form of the effect of transformational leadership (X₁) on educators' performances (Y) had the following regression equation: $\hat{Y} = 74.626 + 0.346 X_1$. Based on the results of statistical test above, it can be seen that the hypothesis of the effect of transformational leadership on educators' performances was acceptable. This can be seen from the results of the t test calculation where $t_c > t_t$ ($12.618 > 1.645$). And based on the results of the calculation of the product moment correlation coefficient formula, it showed that $r_c > r_t$ ($0.587 > 0.113$) meaning that it can be said that there was positive influence on transformational leadership with educators' performances, with determination coefficient of $r^2_{X_1Y} = 0.344$. This meant that 34.4% of the variation in educators' performances (Y) was influenced by transformational leadership (X₁).

The results of this study were in accordance with Wirawan's opinion who said that leadership has important role in someone's effort in playing his role as a leader in order to influence other people in certain organization/institution to achieve its goals (Juliadi & Virlia, 2015). This study showed that there was positive influence between transformational leadership on educators' performances. Therefore, it can be concluded that if the transformational leadership went well, the better the educators' performances and vice versa.

The Effect of X₂ (Adversity Quotient) on Y (Educators' Performances)

Based on the simple linear regression analysis with pairs of data between adversity quotient variable (X₂) and educators' performances variable (Y) produced regression coefficient 0.181 and constant of 108.665. Thus, the form of the effect of adversity quotient (X₂) on educators' performances (Y) had the following regression equation: $\hat{Y} = 108.665 + 0.181 X_2$. Based on the results of statistical test above, it can be seen that the hypothesis of the effect of adversity quotient on educators' performances was acceptable. This can be seen from the results of the t test calculation where $t_c > t_t$ ($6.121 > 1.645$). And based on the results of the calculation of the product moment correlation coefficient formula, it showed that $r_c > r_t$ ($0.332 > 0.113$) meaning that it can be said that there was positive influence on adversity quotient with educators' performances, with determination coefficient of $r^2_{X_2Y} = 0.110$. This meant that 11.0% of the variation in educators' performances (Y) was influenced by adversity quotient (X₂).

The results of this study were in accordance with Sinamo's opinion that work ethic is formed from person's intellectual ability to live the life (Robianto, Masdupi, & Syahrizal, 2020). This intellectual ability is then transformed into a doctrine

that is used as a basis for work. This doctrine will determine person's degree of responsibility in carrying out tasks. This research showed that there was positive influence between adversity quotient and educators professionalism on institution culture. So, it can be concluded that the higher/stronger adversity quotient and educators professionalism, the higher/stronger the institution culture.

The Effect of X_3 (Competency) on Y (Educators' Performances)

Based on the simple linear regression analysis with pairs of data between competency variable (X_3) and educators' performances variable (Y) produced regression coefficient 0.741 and constant of -1.780. Thus, the form of the effect of competency (X_3) on educators' performances (Y) had the following regression equation: $\hat{Y} = -1,780 + 0,741 X_3$. Based on the results of statistical test above, it can be seen that the hypothesis of the effect of competency on educators' performances was acceptable. This can be seen from the results of the t test calculation where $t_c > t_t$ ($34.761 > 1.645$). And based on the results of the calculation of the product moment correlation coefficient formula, it showed that $r_c > r_t$ ($0.894 > 0.113$) meaning that it can be said that there was positive influence on competency with educators' performances, with determination coefficient of $r^2_{X_3Y} = 0.800$. This meant that 80.0% of the variation in educators' performances (Y) was influenced by competency (X_3).

The results of this study were in accordance with Wirawan's opinion about commitment to work (Nasution, Karina, Sembiring, & Harahap, 2021). Work ethic has influence on commitment to work. People who have high work ethic are also highly committed to their work. This study showed that the competency of the educators was in good category, and the educators' performances were in the high category. So, it can be concluded that there was positive influence of competency on educators' performances.

The Effect of X_1 (Transformational Leadership) on X_3 (Competency)

Based on the simple linear regression analysis with pairs of data between transformational leadership variable (X_1) and competency variable (X_3), it produced regression coefficient 0.420 and constant of 110.854. Thus, the form of the effect of transformational leadership (X_1) on competency (X_3) had the following regression equation: $\hat{Y} = 110.854 + 0.420 X_3$. Based on the results of statistical test above, it can be seen that the hypothesis of the effect of transformational leadership on competency was acceptable. This can be seen from the results of the t test calculation where $t_c > t_t$ ($12.750 > 1.645$). And based on the results of the calculation of the product moment correlation coefficient formula, it showed that $r_c > r_t$ ($0.591 > 0.113$) meaning that it can be said that there was positive influence on transformational leadership with competency, with determination coefficient of $r^2_{X_{13}} = 0.349$. This meant that 34.9% of the variation in competency (X_3) was influenced by transformational leadership (X_1).

The results of this study were in accordance with Kartono's opinion that leadership appears and develops as a result of automatic interactions between leaders and the individuals being led (Suhartono, Subagja, & Rusdah, 2020). This leadership can be functioned on the basis of the leader's power to invite, influence and tell other people to do something, for the achievement of a certain goal.

The Effect of X_2 (Adversity Quotient) on X_3 (Competency)

Based on the simple linear regression analysis with pairs of data between adversity quotient variable (X_2) and competency variable (X_3), it produced regression coefficient 0.193 and constant of 155.577. Thus, the form of the effect of adversity quotient (X_2) on competency (X_3) had the following regression equation: $\hat{Y} = 155.577 + 0.193 X_3$. Based on the results of statistical test above, it can be seen that the hypothesis of the effect of adversity quotient on competency was acceptable. This can be seen from the results of the t test calculation where $t_c > t_t$ ($5.362 > 1.645$). And based on the results of the calculation of the product moment correlation coefficient formula, it showed that $r_c > r_t$ ($0.294 > 0.113$) meaning that it can be said that there was positive influence on adversity quotient with competency, with determination coefficient of $r^2_{X_{23}} = 0.087$. This meant that 8.7% of the variation in competency (X_3) was influenced by adversity quotient (X_2).

The results of this study were in accordance with Stoltz's statement as quoted by Said in his preamble, "*with the existence of AQ, every human being always manifests a basic urge to continue to ascent or advance so that they continue to face obstacles*" (Ahyani, 2016).

The Effect of X_1 (Transformational Leadership) on X_2 (Adversity Quotient)

Based on the simple linear regression analysis with pairs of data between transformational leadership variable (X_1) and adversity quotient variable (X_2), it produced regression coefficient 0.322 and constant of 75.671. Thus, the form of the effect of transformational leadership (X_1) on adversity quotient (X_2) had the following regression equation: $\hat{Y} = 75.671 + 0.322 X_2$. Based on the results of statistical test above, it can be seen that the hypothesis of the effect of adversity quotient on competency was acceptable. This can be seen from the results of the t test calculation where $t_c > t_t$ ($5.424 > 1.645$). And based on the results of the calculation of the product moment correlation coefficient formula, it showed that $r_c > r_t$

(0.294 > 0.113) meaning that it can be said that there was positive influence on transformational leadership with adversity quotient, with determination coefficient of $r^2_{X_{12}} = 0.088$. This meant that 8.8% of the variation in adversity quotient (X_2) was influenced by transformational leadership (X_1).

The results of this study were in accordance with Rivai stated the overall pattern of a leader's actions is both visible and invisible to his subordinates. Leadership style describes a consistent combination of philosophies, skills, traits and attitudes that underlie someone's behavior (D.G.E.S, 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research analysis, it can be concluded as follows:

1. There was direct positive effect of transformational leadership on the Polri educators' performances. This meant that the more positive the transformational leadership, the better Polri educators' performances.
2. There was direct positive effect of adversity quotient on the Polri educators' performances. This meant that the more effective the adversity quotient, the better the performances.
3. There was direct positive effect of competency on the Polri educators' performances. This meant that the more positive the competency, the more effective the performances will be.
4. There was direct positive effect of transformational leadership on the Polri educators' competency. This gave an understanding that the more positive the transformational leadership, the more effective the competency.
5. There was direct positive effect of adversity quotient on the Polri educators' competency. It can be said that the more positive the adversity quotient is, the more effective the competency.
6. There was direct positive effect of transformational leadership on the adversity quotient of the Polri educators. The more positive the transformational leadership, the more effective the adversity quotient.

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